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Shikshamitra

शिक्षामित्र

पत्रकार परिषद् (उ.प्र.) आगरा द्वारा पत्रिका दिवस पर आयोजित गोष्ठी में विशिष्टजन-सत्येन्द्र पाठक, नेविल स्मिथ, अनूप जिन्दल, प्रो० (डॉ०) गिरजा शंकर शर्मा, विधायक जगन प्रसाद गर्ग, आई०जी० (आगरा जोन) श्री आशुतोष पाण्डेय (मुख्य अतिथि), डॉ० विजय अग्रवाल (अध्यक्ष), डॉ० महेश भार्गव, के०पी० सिंह (प्रदेश महामंत्री)

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शिक्षामित्र—त्रैमासिक में समस्त प्रकाशित सामग्री का कॉपीराइट पत्रिका का होगा तथा इसमें प्रकाशित सभी साहित्य के तथ्यों तथा विचारों की प्रस्तुति की जिम्मेदारी लेखक या रचनाकार की होगी इसके लिये सम्पादक का कोई दायित्व नहीं है।

विवाद की स्थिति में आगरा न्यायालय मान्य होगा।

सम्पादक : विवेक भार्गव

स्वामी, प्रकाशक, मुद्रक एवं सम्पादक —
विवेक भार्गव, 4/230, कचहरी घाट,
आगरा-282 004 के लिये राष्ट्रभाषा
ऑफसेट प्रेस, 26/471, बल्का बस्ती,
राजामंडी, आगरा-282 002 द्वारा मुद्रित।

Education for Peace & Harmony

Rajshree

Present human society is still pervaded by large scale violence, tension and absence of peace at all levels. Last hundred years has been particularly violent and bloody. World wars alone have killed nearly 100 million peoples, bulk of them innocent non-combatants. There are gun culture, nacro terrorism, social, armed mafias and terrorism in modern world. We live in an age of unprecedented violence, locally, nationally and globally.

"If we are to teach real peace in the world we shall have to begin with children"

—**Mahatma Gandhi**

Peace is a way of living together, in which poeple give their fellow creatures the space and, if necessary, the mutual support to live their lives to the full. Peace education may be defined as the process of acquiring the values, the knowledge and developing the attitudes, skills and behaviours to live in harmony with oneself, with other and with the natural environment.

Education for peace is different from peace education. In the latter, peace is a subject in the syllabus. In the former, peace becomes the shaping vision of education. This implies a paradigm shifts in the total transation of education. Currently, the enterprise of education is driven by the market forces. Education for peace is not antagonistic to the market, but it does not recognize the market as the purpose of education. The market is only a part of our life-world. Education for peace is education for life, and not merely for a livelihood. Equipping individuals with the values, skills and attitudes they need to be whole some persons who live in harmony with others and as responsible citizens is the goal of the education for peace.

Education for peace is pioneering move, must be implemented with vision and determination. Peace is the shaping vision of education. It is for life. Peace means freedom from mental agitation or anxiety or the absence of cessation of war or condition of the order or harmony. Peace ensures an education that makes an individuals citizen and creates a learning environment to live in harmony with adjacent nature and act cooperatively. At present the need of education for peace is peace of mind, peace in the family, peace in society, peace between nations and peace in the universe.

Education for peace seeks to nurture ethical development, including the values, attitudes and skills required for living in harmony with oneself and with others, including nature and as responsible citizen is the goal of education for peace and Report of International commission of education for the 21st Century, UNESCO (1996) says, "living together in harmony" must be the ultimate goal of education in the 21st century - Learning the treasure within. It clearly reiterate the importance of peace in education and show that peace is an integrative perspectives for the school curriculum as Mahatma Gandhi also says "If we are to teach peace in the world we shall have to begin with children" and peace building could be excellent plan/strategy for education present day society. Therefore schools can be nurseries for peace, its curriculum should be for education peace, and the purpose of education here goes beyond the propagation of knowledge. It is education for life, live in harmony with others.

From ancient time our society used to give a lot of regards to teachers. Teacher has main role in once's life as Dronacharya for Eklavya, and Arjun, Ramdas for Shiva Ji, Chankya for

Chandragupta Maurya and so on. India is also considered as Guru of world because of worshiper of peace and harmony. It was proved by Swami Vivekanand at Chicago. Today India is passing through a series of crises. Today education is considered as a subject of investment. The role of teacher is as manager or investor. Quality and quantity of production is depends on manager or teacher and factory or academic institution. Today all of us face of poverty, over population, pollution and terrorism etc. at the time of such crises we should adopt the maxim of Ahinsa. Ahinsa is a RAMRAJYA which dreamed by Mahatma Gandhi. Whenever we forget our morality and peace we have to face to a series cries.

World also face two world wars and India faced Pakistan and China war in modern history. The result of this was so harmful which can looks in our face today. Someone said that "If you want peace you must understand war". We must adopt peace in our education if we want to develop our society. For all this teachers have to take hard and fast step because he is brain of our society and ideal of human.

The glorious past of our society and country have valuable tradition one of such golden tradition was the respect which was given to the all. Gift of education was, considered to be the best gift in our society, given by teacher. Teacher is placed at the top of social leader; because he encouraged learning in society and gave wisdom to his pupils he was the intellectual and spiritual father of his disciples leading them ignorance to knowledge. Buddha, Jain was regarded the greatest and ideal teachers in ancient India no doubt lived in poverty, but were highly respected by society. There are Guru is no less then God. Sant Dadu, Kabir, Nanak, Tulsidas, Surdas described the importance of Guru. Guru was worshiped by princes, kings, warriors, politicians, sportsment and businessmen. Teacher should be done work peacefully for peace.

Teacher as Peace Builder

For students, teachers are role-models, Therefore, teachers play a role, unwittingly, in propagating violence if they are not oriented to peace. As the saying goes, "what I teach is what I know and what I educate is what I am". A teacher's prime responsibility is to help students becomes good human being; motivated to fulfil their true potential not only for their own benefit but also for the betterment of the society as a whole. It is for this reason that a teacher is compared to a gardener who plants seed of knowledge and good values, waters them with care and kindness and removes weed of ignorance. Good teachers are models of peace values, such as, the art of listening, the humility to acknowledgement and correct one's mistake, assuming responsibility for one's actions, sharing concerns and helping each other to solve problems transcending differences, even if they do not preach peace. This picture shows some qualities of a good teacher.

A teacher who imposes discipline in the class room only by intimidating students with blows and slaps is a role model for violence as the sole problem-solving strategy. The teacher's role in the creating a positive climate in the classroom is of paramount importance. It is his/her attitudes, values and relationship that determine the nature

of the classroom climate. A teacher who, from a peace perspective, can critically evaluate his/her attitudes, habitual modes of thinking and approach to teaching what one teachers and what are the carry over values of what is taught and how it is taught is an asset for education for peace.

Teacher can act as peace builders being themselves example of social healing, engaging their responsibilities from enlarged perspective of peace.

Pedagogical Skills and Strategies

The common pedagogic goal for teachers is syllabus and examination oriented. In peace oriented pedagogy, the focus is not merely on retention concepts, memorization of texts achieving individual goals and excellence but on learning to reflects, shares, care and collaborate with other. Every topic/lesson has peace laden components, which need to be transacted with deliberate planning from a positive and humanistic perspective. The methods of teaching should be creative, child-centred, largely experimental and participatory. These include creation of appropriate learning experiences, discussion, debates, presentation and group and cooperative projects, depending on students maturity levels and the subject content. The teacher and school may devise other context specific strategies to develop among students a sense of openness and comprehension about diverse cultures, histories and fundamental shares values. There is ample scope in the syllabi of various subject areas for teaching students the importance of adopting peaceful means of resolving disagreement and conflicts and eschewing violence, and teachers need to take full advantage of this.

Presenting lessons from a humanistic and positive perspective is the basis of education. Teaching should awaken positive feeling and foster positive experience, help in arriving at an understanding of the self, encourage openness

to inquiry by raising question, exploring, discovering, constructing and understanding the values and provide an opportunity for applying the knowledge of values the student has learnt. Strategies like question, stories, anecdotes, games, experiments, discussion, dialogues, value-clarification, examples, analogies, role-play and simulation are helpful in promoting peace through teaching learning. Some peace value may be more appropriate strategies vis-a-vis values need to be delineated.

In all of this, what stands out is the crucial role that the teacher plays in an approach to education that promotes a culture of peace. The fact that learning has to necessarily be pupil oriented does not contradict this. Learning can be pupil oriented only if the teacher facilitates it. It would be naive to understand the pupil-oriented approach in a way that devalues the role that the teacher plays in the learning process. For education for peace, a great deal depends on the peace-motivation of teachers, especially in the integrated approach. The teacher has to be alert to peace opportunities and creative in appropriating them in respect of the curriculum as a whole. Teachers who are either aggressive or indifferent to the culture of peace, and hence see teaching only as the warehousing of information, may remain blind to the exciting scope that every lesson and every experience in the school offers to promote the cause of peace.

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